

Prime Number Trend

Analysis: Correlation of n^{th} prime number and n

Research Paper

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Yours truly,
Akshay Singh Bchehhat

Abstract

This research explores a trend in prime numbers. By analyzing the Ratios and comparing their differences to a conclusion, this study identifies a logarithmic trend in prime number ratios and proposes a formula linking the mean difference to $\ln(k)$.

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Introduction

When the Ratio of the n^{th} prime number is taken with n where $n=a^m$.
(Here “a” is a constant and m belongs to natural number.)

Then an increase is noticed which is very similar. This difference in Ratio changes with “a”. The main thing to be noticed is that the increase is very similar for a few values of “a”.

We will try to draw a correlation, variance of the Ratios, and difference to get a hold over this trend.

Background

While prime numbers are historically regarded as unpredictable, recent computational analyses suggest localized patterns. This spiked my curiosity.

I was once curious to see if there is no trend in prime numbers. So I looked up their list and found a pattern and when I started to investigate it. I found that it was pretty accurate as it maintained a certain level of variance and correlation. Although it was not 100% accurate, there will be some trend which might be useful in future. Therefore, this research opens a big door to great research in the future.

And I hope that it serves as the foundation of great acknowledgements in the future.

Context

We are going to start our analysis of Ratios of n^{th} prime number with n where $n=a^m$.

(Here “a” is a constant and m belongs to natural number.)

Let’s start it by putting the values of “a” and we will use $m=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7,$ and 8 . We are currently doing it for a small range as a certain value raised to a power of 8 often gives a very large value n , and we will use the n^{th} prime number, which will be even bigger. Also, keeping a small range of m will help us analyze more values of “a”.

Let’s start with $a=2$

m	$n = 2^m$	n^{th} Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	2	3	1.5	–
2	4	7	1.75	0.25
3	8	19	2.375	0.625
4	16	53	3.3125	0.9375
5	32	131	4.09375	0.78125
6	64	311	4.859375	0.765625
7	128	719	5.6171875	0.7578125
8	256	1619	6.32421875	0.70703125

The difference started to decline slowly after a rise till $m=4$.
 The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between m and Ratio is 0.9954.
 The mean and variance of differences are 0.6892 & 0.0397,
 respectively.

$a=3$

m	$n = 3^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	3	5	1.6667	—
2	9	23	2.5556	0.8889
3	27	103	3.8148	1.2593
4	81	419	5.1728	1.3580
5	243	1543	6.3498	1.1770
6	729	5519	7.5706	1.2209
7	2187	19289	8.8198	1.2492
8	6561	65687	10.0117	1.1919

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9995.

The mean and variance of differences is found to be 1.1922 & 0.0183.

a=4

m	$n = 4^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	4	7	1.7500	—
2	16	53	3.3125	1.5625
3	64	311	4.8594	1.5469
4	256	1619	6.3242	1.4648
5	1024	8161	7.9697	1.6455
6	4096	38873	9.4905	1.5208
7	16384	180503	11.0170	1.5266
8	65536	821641	12.5372	1.5202

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.99996.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 1.5410 & 0.00276.

a=5

m	$n = 5^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	5	11	2.2	—
2	25	97	3.88	1.68
3	125	691	5.528	1.648
4	625	4637	7.4192	1.8912
5	3125	28687	9.17984	1.76064
6	15625	171529	10.977856	1.79802
7	78125	994837	12.7339136	1.75606
8	390625	5653807	14.47374592	1.73983

Graph of m vs. Ratio

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9999.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 1.7534 & 0.0053.

a=6

m	$n = 6^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	6	13	2.1667	—
2	36	151	4.1944	2.0278
3	216	1321	6.1157	1.9213
4	1296	10627	8.1998	2.0841
5	7776	79349	10.2043	2.0045
6	46656	567871	12.1714	1.9671
7	279936	3950183	14.1110	1.9396
8	1679616	26941241	16.0401	1.9291

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9996.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 1.9819 & 0.0031.

a=7

m	$n = 7^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	7	17	2.4286	—
2	49	227	4.6327	2.2041
3	343	2309	6.7318	2.0991
4	2401	21391	8.9092	2.1774
5	16807	185707	11.0494	2.1402
6	117649	1549817	13.1732	2.1238
7	823543	12579617	15.2750	2.1018
8	5764801	100061641	17.3573	2.0823

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9993.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.1327 & 0.0017.

a=8

m	$n = 8^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	8	19	2.3750	—
2	64	311	4.8594	2.4844
3	512	3671	7.1699	2.3105
4	4096	38873	9.4905	2.3206
5	32768	386093	11.7826	2.2921
6	262144	3681131	14.0424	2.2598
7	2097152	34136029	16.2773	2.2349
8	16777216	310248241	18.4922	2.2149

Graph of m vs. Ratio

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is found to be 0.9995.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.3025 & 0.0068.

a=9

m	$n = 9^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	9	23	2.5556	—
2	81	419	5.1728	2.6173
3	729	5519	7.5706	2.3978
4	6561	65687	10.0117	2.4411
5	59049	733561	12.4229	2.4112
6	531441	7867547	14.8042	2.3813
7	4782969	82064027	17.1575	2.3534
8	43046721	839001721	19.4905	2.3329

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is found to be 0.9988.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.4193 & 0.0075.

a=10

m	$n = 10^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	10	29	2.9	—
2	100	541	5.41	2.51
3	1000	7919	7.919	2.509
4	10000	104729	10.4729	2.5539
5	100000	1299709	12.99709	2.52419
6	1000000	15485863	15.485863	2.48877
7	10000000	179424673	17.9424673	2.45660
8	100000000	2038074743	20.38074743	2.43828

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9989.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.4973 & 0.0014.

a=11

m	$n = 11^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	11	31	2.8182	—
2	121	661	5.4628	2.6446
3	1331	10957	8.2322	2.7693
4	14641	159521	10.8955	2.6633
5	161051	2176171	13.5123	2.6168
6	1771561	28516039	16.0966	2.5843
7	19487171	363466813	18.6516	2.5550
8	214358881	4540996847	21.1841	2.5325

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9998.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.6237 & 0.0054.

a=14

m	$n = 14^m$	n th Prime	Ratio	Difference
1	14	43	3.0714	—
2	196	1193	6.0867	3.0153
3	2744	24809	9.0412	2.9544
4	38416	459341	11.9570	2.9158
5	537824	7969019	14.8172	2.8601
6	7529536	132830609	17.6413	2.8241
7	105413504	2154271267	20.4364	2.7951
8	1475789056	34252584679	23.2097	2.7733

Graph of m vs. Ratio

The correlation of “m” and “Ratio” is 0.9998.

The mean and variance of differences are found to be 2.8767 & 0.0086.

Base (k)	Mean of Difference	Variance of Difference
2	0.6892	0.0397
3	1.1922	0.0183
4	1.5410	0.0026
5	1.7534	0.0053
6	1.9819	0.0031
7	2.1327	0.0017
8	2.3025	0.0068
9	2.4193	0.0075
10	2.4973	0.0014
11	2.6237	0.0054
14	2.8767	0.0086

As we know, according to the Prime number Theorem, the rate slowly increases with $\ln(k)$.

So now let's check the value of mean and $\ln(k)$ for respective "k".

And then we will check the ratio of the mean and $\ln(k)$. To see the deviation of our observation and earlier stated theorem.

Base (k)	Mean of Difference	Variance of Difference	$\ln(k)$	Mean / $\ln(k)$
2	0.6892	0.0397	0.6931	0.9942
3	1.1922	0.0183	1.0986	1.0852
4	1.5410	0.0026	1.3863	1.1117
5	1.7534	0.0053	1.6094	1.0896
6	1.9819	0.0031	1.7918	1.1061
7	2.1327	0.0017	1.9459	1.0960
8	2.3025	0.0068	2.0794	1.1072
9	2.4193	0.0075	2.1972	1.1010
10	2.4973	0.0014	2.3026	1.0847
11	2.6237	0.0054	2.3979	1.0942
14	2.8767	0.0086	2.6391	1.0901

We can see that the ratio of “Mean of difference” and “ $\ln(k)$ ” is very close to 1, but it is not 1, so we will make some amendments to make it more accurate. We can see the value of the ratio is less than 1 for “ $k=2$ ” only and more than 1 for other “ k ”. This shows that there might be an involvement of $\ln(k)$ further in this ratio for better precision. As 2 is less than e giving value less than 1. But it stayed close to one and had a pretty uniform trend for bigger value. This shows that there might be an involvement of $(\ln(k))^{1/k}$.

When we plot a graph of these 2.

We get a correlation of 0.9995.

Even though the correlation is 0.9995.

The ratio of the Mean of Difference to $\ln(k)$ approximates 1.089, suggesting a consistent scaling factor.

We can try to make it very close to 1 for better precision.

Let's compare the value of the ratio of "Mean of difference" and $\ln(k)$ with the value of $(\ln(k))^{1/k}$.

Base (k)	Mean of Difference	Variance of Difference	$\ln(k)$	Mean / $\ln(k)$	$(\ln(k))^{1/k}$
2	0.6892	0.0397	0.6931	0.9942	0.8326
3	1.1922	0.0183	1.0986	1.0852	1.0319
4	1.5410	0.0026	1.3863	1.1117	1.0834
5	1.7534	0.0053	1.6094	1.0896	1.1070
6	1.9819	0.0031	1.7918	1.1061	1.1179
7	2.1327	0.0017	1.9459	1.0960	1.1236
8	2.3025	0.0068	2.0794	1.1072	1.1267
9	2.4193	0.0075	2.1972	1.1010	1.1282
10	2.4973	0.0014	2.3026	1.0847	1.1287
11	2.6237	0.0054	2.3979	1.0942	1.1287
14	2.8767	0.0086	2.6391	1.0901	1.1287

Now we can see that the ratios of Mean of Differences and $\ln(k)$ is very close to $(\ln(k))^{1/k}$. This means we have got a value very close to the mean of difference and this might be the exact value as well.

As this value of mean of difference is calculated with limited resources and with the help of my friend Rounak. But this is for sure an achievement opening the door for future research.

As of now, the value of :

$$\text{Mean of Difference} \approx \ln(k) * (\ln(k))^{1/k} = \ln(k)^{(k+1)/k}$$

This trend might be absolute as well.

We tried this for limited values of m & a because of limited value.

But this will surely be the base of many future researches in the field of unpredictability of PRIME NUMBERS.

Key Issues & Challenges

The limited resources were surely an issue. Calculating the 1,475,789,056th prime required approximations due to resource constraints. Some minor mistakes in calculation might also be there, but overall, the trend is pretty robust. Also, the correlation of many graphs was very close to 1. But it was not absolute 1 for any of the graph. This is obviously because of the nature of prime numbers. But even after all this the result obtained is very promising and gives hopes for future research.

Solutions & Recommendations

A solution of inability to find the correlation of absolute 1, can be to try verifying this formula for bigger values as I am pretty sure that all the trends stated will surely approach the result stated by me which is ***Mean of Difference $\approx \ln(k) * (\ln(k))^{1/k} = \ln(k)^{(k+1)/k}$*** . The trend goes in that direction as well. Another possibility is that the value stated by the formula that I gave will act as an asymptote, which means that it will continue to reach it and will meet it at infinity (imaginary intersection)

Conclusion

This research reveals a closer logarithmic trend in prime number ratios, offering a potential bridge between empirical observation and theoretical frameworks. This might be a trend which give the value of a prime number, but this will definitely help us to find multiple results regarding infinite series of prime numbers.

Mean of difference of consecutive ratio n^{th} prime number and $n = \ln(k) * (\ln(k))^{1/k} = \ln(k)^{(k+1)/k}$

(Where $n=k^m$ and m belongs to natural number.)